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NANOFACTS
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“NETWORKING ACTIVITIES FOR NANOTECHNOLOGY-FACILITATED CANCER THERANOSTICS”

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1. Summary

NANOFACTS (Networking Activities for Nanotechnology-Facilitated Cancer Theranostics) is a project aimed to enhance the excellence of Biosense institute (BIOS), University of Novi Sad, Serbia, in research on cancer theranostic nanomaterials and cancer diagnostics, and to promote collaboration with internationally leading institutions at EU level. To widen the research agenda at BIOS with cancer-related research and health-related biosensing technologies, **NANOFACTS** will harness and improve the pre-existing links with two leading European research institutions in the field of nanotechnology and development of biosensors:

- Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Ireland, The School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, experienced in application of nanotechnology for cancer treatment and imaging; and its validation, including biocompatibility of nanoparticles/nanodevices.
- Vienna University of Technology (TUW), Faculty of Technical Chemistry, Institute of Applied Synthetic Chemistry and Institute of Chemical Technologies and Analytics, with an expertise in devising health-related biosensors.

Different types of training visits are planned between the beneficiaries which will enable BIOS researchers to acquire specific scientific and technological (S&T) skills toward addressing the identified gaps and enhance the expertise in cancer-related research at BIOS. TCD has unique expertise in translational research, which spans the entire spectrum from cellular based approaches, *in vivo* animal models to patient-orientated research, whereas the latest initiative of TUW is the establishment of a lab on a chip laboratory for bioscience technologies that combines aspects of microfluidics, material sciences, biosensing technologies and cell biology. In that sense, capacity-building measures for S&T skill transfer will be undertaken through staff exchange activities and trainings to gain hands-on knowledge about the construction and development of cancer theranostic nanomaterials and biosensors for detection of cancer-specific molecules.

NANOFACTS's Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) is the core document providing an overview of the strategy and the activities that will be implemented to disseminate, communicate, and exploit the **NANOFACTS** project's achievements. PEDR will clarify when and what actions will be undertaken by the project's consortium and will identify the target groups, tools, media and distribution channels, while maintaining a wise balance of online and offline activities. Its objective is to increase the public awareness of the project and foster acceptance and uptake of innovations and the knowledge created throughout the project. Good practices set within the scope of the project will serve as the basis for future activities beyond the project's duration. In Serbia, the Widening country, the research activities covered by **NANOFACTS** are poorly developed, mostly due to restraints regarding the infrastructure and research funding. **One of the project's goals is to widen the research agenda at BIOS with cancer-related research and health-related biosensing technologies.**

The PEDR will therefore take special care in designing suitable dissemination tools and activities for involving and engaging the target groups (academic community, clinicians, cancer patient advocacy and interest groups, industry and general public) in the project activities since the very beginning. Messages that the project will convey will be tailored to the different target groups, their profiles and channels of communication that they are using, so that the impact would be maximised.

Although BIOS is the leader in the WP6 and the institution responsible for development of this PEDR, the PEDR is the result of collaborative work between the partners. TCD and TUW certainly possess great experience in scientific terms, but their experience in engaging the community and supporting the acceptance of new technologies and new business models will be also invaluable. Through different types of discussions (online discussions, face-to-face meetings) held during the project events, BIOS will also learn from partners' positive experiences regarding the exploitation and dissemination of results.

2. Aim and Objectives of NANOFACTS's Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

Basic aim of PEDR is to maximise the project's impact. It is directed towards promotion of **NANOFACTS**'s achievements and results to a wide audience including students, researchers, industry representatives, health and pharmaceutical sectors, policy makers and other relevant stakeholders. In this way, we are:

- a) spreading the knowledge through NANOFACTS activities that will in turn enable further scientific breakthroughs and technological advances;
- b) generating new ideas and products;
- c) raising awareness about huge positive impact on human health and socio-economic impacts that new technologies create.

NANOFACTS's PEDR will be a practical tool for efficient implementation of dissemination activities. Its concrete objectives are following:

- 1. To promote BIOS as the regional leader in multi-disciplinary research on construction of nanomaterials for application in cancer theranostics and cancer-related biosensing.** BioSense has already had a lot of success in multi-disciplinary research and application of different nanomaterials for devising biosensors in the agriculture- related research. However, the technology has not been applied for cancer-related research. **NANOFACTS** will increase BIOS's research portfolio and innovative capacity and support the development of products and services. This will position BIOS as the regional hub for cancer-related scientific excellence.
- 2. To grow the visibility of the new BIOS knowledge and skills.** Excellent science and high-tech innovations are crucial, but their promotion may be equally important, as the best scientific works often end up unnoticed by the practitioners. **NANOFACTS** will enhance visibility of research activities at BIOS through connection of its members with TCD and TUW researchers, through organisation of project events, which will include new stakeholders, but also through increased scientific capacity. As cancer-related research at BIOS becomes more and more advanced and relevant in the science community, the visibility of the group will witness a major growth.
- 3. To promote NANOFACTS project results and raise awareness of the cancer nanotheranostic technologies in Serbia and the region.** BioSense is already recognised in Serbia and the Balkans as the key-player for development and implementation of biosensing technologies, especially through organisation of the Open Days of the Digital Farm and AgroSense, a free online platform for farm management. The Open Days attracted hundreds of visitors including farmers, government representatives and other stakeholders in the past season and AgroSense has got more than 10,000 active users. They, along with the regular coverage on TV, radio and social media, serve as the main channels for communication with the stakeholders. **NANOFACTS** will utilise these communication channels to convey new cancer-related research paradigm at BIOS.
- 4. To establish new and maintain existing collaborations with key stakeholders.** Firstly, the workshops, Training school and other project activities will gather our existing partners with whom we have already developed mutual trust through H2020 projects, EBRD's Green Vouchers, field trials, scientific and all other projects. They will be involved mostly through personal contacts, while we will rely on other channels of communication to involve new stakeholders in the aforementioned events. Although these events are interesting on their own, they will be a chance to introduce BIOS to the new stakeholders, recognise practical problems that can be solved using nanotheranostics approach and discuss opportunities for further collaboration.
- 5. To advance internationalisation and partnerships and prepare roadmap for future joint projects.** Workshops, Training school and researcher visits will have a significant international character.

They will create new links between people from various scientific fields, backgrounds and countries and diversity is well-known to spark innovations. There are numerous problems in the development of new technologies for cancer theranostics and their implementation that need to be tackled. Fortunately, good ideas can be backed up by financing coming from company’s own funds, European funding schemes, national ministries and innovation funds and they will make sure that BIOS’s growth is indeed sustainable.

The dissemination strategy of **NANOFACTS** captures the partners’ strategy and concrete actions related to the dissemination and exploitation of the project results. This strategy is, on one hand, designed to target the scientific community, industry (in particular pharmaceutical companies) and potential users (patients), to create positive impacts in science, industrial leadership and employability, and to help **enhance the excellence of research in the area of nanotechnology-facilitated cancer treatment, imaging and diagnostics** in Serbia, as well as in the rest of Europe. On the other hand, the dissemination targets students with the aim to endorse their specialization in this topic and ensure the critical mass of prominent researchers that will contribute to the development of the knowledge-based society. Patients are another crucial target group, since the improvement of their understanding of cancer research-related science plays dominant role in making positive decisions and direct engagement in studies, also allowing researchers to better understand patients’ interests and priorities. General public needs to be well informed about the latest cancer-related research directions and potentials for improvement of current practices.

The strategy intends to raise awareness and interest on scientific advances and developed technologies among the target groups. Our dissemination and communication plan will foster cross-border and cross-sectorial cooperation with the final goal on gaining new knowledge in creating novel technologies in cancer research and implementation thereof. Dissemination KPIs are represented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: NANOFACTS Dissemination KPIs

Channel	Tools to be used in NANOFACTS	Success indicator	Target value
ELECTRONIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Social media: Twitter account, LinkedIn group, Facebook page, Instagram page Radio and TV appearances 	Number of website views	3000
		Number of followers on social media accounts	300
		Number of media appearances	4
PRINTED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publications in high-impact scientific journals Project brochure Leaflets for project results Press releases and articles in newspapers and magazines 	Number of journal publications	20
		Number of distributed brochures	3 circulations (200 each)
		Number of distributed leaflets	1 circulation (200)
		Number of press releases	10
EVENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Various dissemination and networking events (exhibitions, science fairs, trade fairs, info days...) Scientific conferences Training school project Workshops 	Number of events with NANOFACTS participation	20
		Number of conference publications	12
		Number of workshops and participants per workshop	3 workshops (each 30 participants)
		Training school	1 training school, 50 participants
FACE-TO-FACE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visits to partner institutions and their collaborators Extended stay visits of ESRs Industry relations Info days 	Number of meetings with partners and collaborators	20
		Number of ESR visits	15
		Number of meeting with industrial partners	4

3. Target Groups

NANOFACTS consortium has a well-established and validated set of dissemination strategies that are reaching a wide spectrum of stakeholders as an integral part of its institutional principles. From experience, successful dissemination requires differentiation of stakeholder groups and targeted efforts designed to resonate with their values, convictions, and attitudes.

Each stakeholder group has its own level of interest and awareness of science and innovation. The strategy of this PEDR is to leverage available dissemination resources and channels to catalyse action of already involved groups and raise awareness and interest in insufficiently involved groups. The major focus is to ensure that the project outcomes are widely disseminated to appropriate target communities (i.e. target groups), at appropriate times (respecting the proposed project timeline), and via appropriate methods (means of information disclosure, intensity, etc.).

The value chain has been thoroughly analysed and the target groups have been defined. They are listed in **Table 2**, along with a short list of concrete content to be communicated and the expected impact.

Table 2: List of NANOFACTS Target Groups and Expected Impact

Target Group	Content to be communicated	Expected impact
Research community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific breakthroughs Newly generated knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spreading new knowledge, creating new channels for future collaboration, generating ideas for innovative products Boosting the process of generating new scientific results in relevant fields High visibility of the project and achieved results, and the excellence of the partners
Young Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific knowledge Technical skills Soft skills Entrepreneurial mentality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advance the knowledge and technical skills of young researchers Advance their soft skills needed to better communicate with different audiences Increase capabilities of converting scientific knowledge and ideas into products and services, creating IPR, writing successful patent applications and setting up spin-offs Promotion of the careers in science and innovation
SMEs and large industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commercial potential of NANOFACTS results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generating ideas for innovative products, transfer of knowledge from academia to industry Higher level of knowledge about latest scientific and technological developments Improved understanding of industry needs by scientists High visibility of the project and achieved results, and the excellence of the partners
Patients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential of NANOFACTS results to positively impact their wellbeing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transfer of knowledge from academia to industry Higher level of knowledge about latest scientific and technological developments Improved understanding of user needs by scientists Improved readiness to approve new technologies for clinical practice

Target Group	Content to be communicated	Expected impact
General Public & Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How NANOFACTS activities can increase the excellence in cancer research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving understanding of cutting-edge science and its impact by general public Higher level of knowledge about latest scientific and technological developments Securing the critical number of scientists of tomorrow by boosting interest of younger population in science High visibility of the project and achieved results, and the excellence of the partners

3.1 Research Community

NANOFACTS will fully exploit the complementary expertise of the consortium and will combine it to achieve interdisciplinary scientific breakthroughs with a wide future impact. Therefore, the **scientific community** is one of the most important and largest target groups in the project. In order to reach the most diverse parts of the community, the **NANOFACTS** consortium will accelerate the spreading of new knowledge by generating advanced discoveries and ideas for innovative products, and by creating new channels for future collaboration. **Major challenge for the PEDR strategy** lies in boosting the process of generating new scientific results in relevant fields, through close collaboration between project partners which are guiding the cutting-edge research in modern science. Successful **collaboration between partners** will result in scientific publications that will ensure high visibility of the project and achieved results.

3.2 Young Researchers

The planned staff exchange programme, **Training School Lectures (TSLs)** and **Workshop Lectures (WSLs)** will educate a new generation of young researchers capable of combining different disciplines and advancing scientific knowledge. **Young researchers** represent a very important target group for **NANOFACTS** project since they constitute a major working force, which will shift the research activities closer to project goals. **NANOFACTS secondments** will enable obtaining both technical and soft-skill training. Newly gained skills, as well as the acquired experience of working in an international setting, will positively influence their careers, while the acquired knowledge as well as established contacts and networking with leading researchers participating in **NANOFACTS** will be highly useful both for completing their **PhD theses** and in their **future careers** and potential further collaborations after the project. Moreover, since academic partners have also a high reputation in education, the dissemination will also take place in the form of lectures for students, i.e. the next generation of scientists, in academic conference and seminars.

3.3 SMEs and Large Industry

Small and medium enterprises, as well as **large industry**, comprise very large and important target group for the **NANOFACTS** project since they offer high potential for commercialization of the project results. Dissemination activities will be devoted to the knowledge exchange from academia to industry as well as vice versa, in order to generate ideas and co-create innovative products using cutting-edge science and technology, while being based on the real-life needs of the end-users. Within such a framework, a higher level of knowledge about the latest scientific and technological developments can significantly expand the portfolio of enterprises and industry partners. The successful outcome of the dissemination strategy should result in high visibility of the project results within the entrepreneur community and leave a large footprint of the **NANOFACTS** essential values. Moreover, to ensure the increased scientific and technological capabilities of Europe in the field of cancer nanotheranostics, project results will be presented during Industry relations Info days and at seminars aimed at gaining the interest from potential industrial partners for possible clinical translation of the Project research outcomes. The SMEs and large industry will be approached on concrete issues with clearly defined goals.

3.4 Patients

The outreach activities will be agreed to promote a conducive environment for the engagement of cancer patients (<http://udruzenjecrc.rs/>, <https://budimozajedno.rs/>, <http://nador.co.rs/>) at **NANOFACTS** events, to enhance the level of **public understanding** of the state-of-the art scientific research. Serbian students will also work on a brochure for cancer patients where **NANOFACTS** and nanomedicine will be presented and written in layman language. This document could be distributed in hospitals and GP cabinets. By widespread dissemination of **NANOFACTS** achievements and through a constant communication with all relevant stakeholders, throughout the project duration and beyond, positive impacts will be ensured in all fields, including healthier population, excellence in science, industrial leadership and employability in science and development, finally contributing to the health of Europe's population, its competitiveness and growth.

3.5 General Public and Media

Finally, the general public is one of the most challenging target groups for the dissemination of advanced scientific results because the dissemination channels should be specially adopted to general knowledge. Involvement of **general public and media** in project activities will ensure continuous focus onto scientific research. Improving understanding of cutting-edge science and its impact on the general public will open new opportunities for future research directions, securing the critical number of scientists of tomorrow by boosting the interest of young people in science. High visibility of the project achieved results and the excellence of partners will clearly demonstrate how **NANOFACTS** research and innovation actions can provide a healthier environment for the society of tomorrow. Most of the dissemination to the general public will be conducted through **layman-language posts** on **social media** and the **NANOFACT website**.

4. Dissemination tools

4.1 Visual identity

The first step of the dissemination and communication activities is the design of a unique and effective visual identity to make the project distinctive and recognizable. Moreover, visual identity has been developed to provide a consistent and clear message about project goals and core values to a widespread audience.

In the view of defining the visual identity of **NANOFACTS**, BIOS team developed initial logo during proposal submission phase shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 1: NANOFACTS Logo, Symbol

All dissemination material will showcase the: **NANOFACTS** logo, the EU emblem, and the clear statement that the project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, through the following text:

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952259."

Visual identity also includes the following templates to be used by all partners as required by the Quality Management Plan:

Figure 2: NANOFACTS Power Point template

Figure 3: NANOFACTS Deliverable template

5. Communication Activities

NANOFACTS has clear communication objectives and a variety of means to achieve them, going much further than to rely solely on standard dissemination actions that are intended to make NANOFACTS project results known to various stakeholder groups.

By communicating tailor-made messaging through the most effective channels to approach targeted audiences, NANOFACTS will reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences (NANOFACTS target groups) while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling some of the most important societal challenges such as cancer therapy, imaging and diagnostics.

The consortium will implement the following key communication activities:

Table 3: Communication channels and tools used in NANOFACTS

Channel	Tools to be used in NANOFACTS
Electronic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web portal • Social media • Radio and TV appearances
Printed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posters • Leaflets • Brochures • Press releases
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training school • Workshops • High impact conferences
Face-to-face meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visits to partner institutions and their collaborators • Extended stay visits of ESRs • Industry relations Info days

5.1 Electronic

Electronic means of communication are by far the most widely spread in the 21st century and are being accessed every day by large number of people. For this reason, they are on the top of the list of **NANOFACTS** communication channels. There are multiple subgroups of the web platforms and they are intended for different purposes.

5.1.1 Website

NANOFACTS website is the first place where a person should be able to find out more about the project’s goals, stages, events, and personnel involved. We setup the initial version of the project website at the address www.nanofacts.net. More detailed website, presenting individual work packages, key people, illustrations representing project’s overview and activities, and recent scientific advances in NANOFACTS-related agenda is in preparation, with the main purpose of illustrating the **NANOFACTS** concept and approach. The website also will serve as a platform for disseminating project results to present **NANOFACTS** publications and other scientific achievements.

Current status is shown through the screenshots from the landing page below.

Figure 4: NANOFACTS's initial website landing page

5.1.2 Social Media

Social media allows dissemination to an extremely wide - but also targeted - audience, maximizing the impact and successful exploitation of our research results. Facebook is the most widely used social media platform in the world. Research from [December 2020](#) shows that there are 1,84 billion daily active users of Facebook. The statistic also shows that there are [4,14 billion active social media users](#), which means that this medium is more than relevant for dissemination & communication within the project. Other widely used social media platforms, such as Instagram and Twitter will be also significant for reaching out to a large number of people. Another social network for professional users is LinkedIn and it is also the one where we will promote our activities. Dissemination & communication within **NANOFACTS** will be concentrated around Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/nanofacts2020/>), Instagram (https://www.instagram.com/_nanofacts/?hl=en), Twitter (<https://twitter.com/NANOFACTS2>), and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/nanofacts>) social networks. Statistics indicate that more than 30 million companies are represented on LinkedIn, which is important because the aim of our project is to provide input on current market demands as well as connection with the end-users. For the promotion of these accounts, we will utilize the accounts of all members of the consortium, which have already gathered a substantial following, and promote **NANOFACTS's** profile on those pages.

Screenshots of **NANOFACTS's** initial website landing page, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Instagram accounts are shown in **Figures 6-10**.

Figure 5: NANOFACTS’s Facebook page

Figure 6: NANOFACTS’s Twitter page

Figure 7: NANOFACTS’s LinkedIn page

Figure 8: NANOFACTS's Instagram page

5.1.3 Radio and TV Appearances

As one of the dissemination goals of NANOFACTS is to approach general public, we will also use the conventional communication channels such as local radio and TV stations. TV and Radio stations with national coverage will be also used to promote our activities to the community by participation in program dedicated to health-related technological development. Another reason why radio and TV appearances are sometimes better than other channels of communication is that most of the people are visual learners. They will remember faces and gestures more than textual information and our young team will promote the youthful and energetic character of BIOS along with the other key messages.

5.2 Printed media

Internet and social media have become increasingly important source of information, especially concerning the fact that in Serbia around 68% of population is using internet. However, this means that around 32% of people are not using internet every day and that this target group should be addressed adequately as well i.e. through printed media. Printed media are also good for addressing general public as they are read in cafés, restaurants, hair studios and similar places visited by the people who are ordinarily not actively involved in science and as such are not aware of the breakthroughs, innovations and options for their use in everyday life. Also, printed materials give a sense of credibility to the project and having them is a part of corporate culture. For this reason, we will print brochures and leaflets which will be distributed during the events.

During the project we will have sets of the activities regarding printed dissemination, and this type of dissemination comprises the following tools and activities:

- Publications in high-impact scientific journals
- Project brochure
- Leaflets for prototypes
- Press releases and articles in newspapers and magazines
- Developing and distributing dissemination material

5.2.1 Publications in high-impact scientific journals and book chapters

Publications in high-impact journals will be the prime tool for dissemination of the research results among the research and academic communities. They will clearly reflect the progress and significant outcomes of the project, and they will enable a new insight into the field of cancer nanotheranostics and biosensing. The **NANOFACTS** project will provide either gold or green open access within 6 months from publication date, and the publications will be deposited into an open repository such as Zenodo. Moreover, the links to publishers' sites and documents will be also available in the project website.

A tentative list of the targeted high-impact journals is given in **Table 4**. We note that we will not publish in all of the listed journals, but the journal will be chosen according to the criterium of how well the achieved result and journal scope are matched. Also, due to the limited budget of the project, we will try to be as economical as possible, and the journal embargo period and article processing charges will be also taken into account. Also, the list of the journals can be updated during the lifetime of the project.

In addition, we note that the actual number of publications may vary from those planned due to the obligations of providing open access and limited budget of the project. Namely, majority (if not all) of the quality journals have embargo period longer than 6 months, which means that the publications will require gold open access and significant amount to be invested into article process charges. However, this potential deviation will not affect the project implementation and outcomes.

Table 4: List of high-impact journals

Journal	Publisher
Nature Materials	Nature
Nature Nanotechnology	Nature
Advanced Materials	Wiley
Advanced Functional Materials	Wiley
Journal of the American Chemical Society	American Chemical Society
ACS Nano	American Chemical Society
Angewandte Chemie (International Edition)	Wiley
Small	Wiley
Journal of Materials Chemistry. A	Royal society of chemistry
Nano letters	American Chemical Society
Chemistry of Materials	American Chemical Society
ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces	American Chemical Society
Nanoscale	Royal Society of Chemistry
Lab-on-Chip	Royal Society of Chemistry
Journal of Materials Chemistry. B	Royal Society of Chemistry
Sensors and Actuators B	Elsevier
Sensors and Actuators A	Elsevier
Biosensors and bioelectronics	Elsevier
IEEE Sensors Journal	IEEE
ACS Sensors	American Chemical Society
Sensors	MDPI
Pharmaceutics	MDPI

5.2.2 Project Brochure

Project brochure will provide a short overview of the project, the project objectives and the expected outcomes. The text of the brochure will be designed to be understandable not only to specialists and professionals, but also to general public. It will introduce the main idea, the approach, and the goals of the

NANOFACTS project. In addition, the brochure will include the project web portal address, information about the consortium and the corresponding logos, and the contact details.

The first version of the brochure will be printed in M6 of the project and it will be used in various occasions including workshops, conferences, networking events, and face-to-face meetings. During the project lifetime, the brochure will be updated accordingly, taking into consideration the results and outcomes. Updated versions of the project brochure are expected to be designed and printed in the second and the third year of the project.

The electronic version of the brochure will be also available on the project website, so it will be circulated electronically as well. The language of the brochure will be English, however if we find it useful, we will also publish brochure in the national languages of the project partners.

5.2.3 Project leaflet

Unlike the project brochure, the project leaflet will be exclusively dedicated to the most tangible outcomes of the project, i.e. to the obtained efficient nanotheranostics and developed prototypes of the microfluidic, lab-on-chip and other types of sensors for cancer diagnostics.

Since the prototypes are planned to be developed in the third year of the project, the leaflet will be designed and published in M30 of the project, to be in line with the project dynamics but also to be available well before the project is concluded.

The leaflet will be used in various occasions including workshops, conferences, networking events, and face-to-face meetings. The electronic version of the brochure will be also available on the project website, so it will be circulated electronically as well. The language of the leaflet will be English.

5.2.4 Press releases and articles in newspapers and magazines

This dissemination tool is aimed at wide audience, rather than only research community. Namely, press articles in local, national, and international newspapers and magazines will raise the public awareness of the project, its impact and outcomes. The articles will be published occasionally, i.e. once the very significant progress is achieved. The press releases will be in form of interviews or technical descriptions of the results, which however will be presented in the form that is understandable to non-specialists. Also, the press released will be archived at the project website.

Since the targeted newspapers and magazines are mostly national, the language of publication will be either English or the national languages of the project partners.

5.2.5 Developing and distributing dissemination material

During the lifetime of the project, a promotional package will be made, including various promotional gadgets and printed office supplies (i.e. pens, folders, notepads, mugs, etc.). This type of promotion is effective in getting the message across to general public, but it also informs the scientific, industry, and other communities.

5.3 Events

Events that will be organised through **NANOFACTS** are an excellent opportunity for networking with targeted audience. Training school and Workshops will gain attention by the scientific and research community and will be a good place for dissemination of both **NANOFACTS**'s activities and achievements. They will also be an excellent opportunity to explain the topics and results of the current research at the BIOS and to get into technical details. Contacts made during these events and high-impact conferences that our researchers will attend, will be essential for promoting BIOS scientific excellence and they will be an excellent breeding ground for setting up paths for future collaboration and joint projects between different teams and institutions. Another important aspect of the events organised/attended within **NANOFACTS** is the

participation of students. **NANOFACTS**'s plan is to grow both during the project and after its end and there is no better place to find new colleagues than the university. Workshops and particularly the Training school would be popular among students and it would be an opportunity to introduce BIOS and **NANOFACTS** to them. Employing local highly motivated students is very beneficial to BIOS as they have a similar mind-set and share similar values, making them very easy to adapt to the BIOS working environment.

Some of the events, that **NANOFACTS**'s researchers plan to attend in the following period are listed below

- Cancer Nanotechnology Gordon Research Conference 2021 - <https://www.grc.org/cancer-nanotechnology-conference/2021/>
- European society for medical oncology (ESMO) Congress 2021 - <https://mr-congress.com/de/kongress-liste/esmo-european-society-for-medical-oncology/>
- American Association for Cancer Researcher Annual meeting 2022 - <https://www.aacr.org/professionals/meetings/future-annual-meetings/>.
- Controlled Release Society Annual Meeting (Virtual): <https://www.controlledreleasesociety.org/events/2021-crs-virtual-annual-meeting>
- Symposium "Nanomaterials for Drug Delivery, Imaging and Immuno-Engineering", XXIX International Materials Research Congress: https://contenido.neored.com/mrs-mexico/call_for_proposals2021.pdf
- NanoBio&Med2021: <http://www.nanobiomedconf.com/NBM21/index.php>
- International Conference On Nanomedicine And Nanobiotechnology – ICONAN 2020 <https://premc.org/conferences/iconan-nanomedicine-nanobiotechnology/>
- 4th International Caparica Christmas Conference on Translational Chemistry 2021 <https://www.ic3tc2021.com/>
- International Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine annual conference: <https://www.ismrm.org/21m/2021-meeting-announcement/>
- 40th World Cancer Conference <https://cancer.global-summit.com/>
- 31st Anniversary World Congress on Biosensors <https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/world-congress-on-biosensors>
- 1st International Electronic Conference on Chemical Sensors and Analytical Chemistry <https://sciforum.net/conference/CSAC2021>
- The Early Detection of Cancer Conference <http://earlydetectionresearch.com/>
- European Researchers' Night TBD
- Science fair TBD

5.4 Face-to-face Meetings

In order to engage stakeholders more directly, **personal interactions will also be a key mean for dissemination**. This specific channel will offer a chance for personal interaction mainly during **researcher visits, info days and workshops/trainings, in trade fairs and exhibitions**, as well as in **professional conferences**. Meetings at professional organizations will provide a unique blend of hands-on experience and direct contact with colleagues from other institutions, which is important for acquiring new skills, for career advancement and networking. Unknown environments are also an opportunity for a spontaneous interaction, which may be very productive. Visits to partner institutions on this project are accompanied by residence programmes and they will be an excellent chance to disseminate **NANOFACTS**'s plans and achievements.

Networking, informal personal meetings with relevant stakeholders at national level, and whenever possible official presentations will be used to present the project results and activities at different stages of project development. The following face-2-face meetings will be pursued:

- Meetings with citizens, students and schoolchildren,
- Meetings during research conferences and at professional organizations (IEEE, RSC...),

- Meetings with other H2020 projects,
- Meetings with other stakeholders.

As stated previously, one of the aims of **NANOFACTS** dissemination is to raise awareness of general public of the **NANOFACTS** project as well as of the importance of research and innovations, and in that manner support development of knowledge-based society. Events such as **Open Days of BioSense Institute, science fairs and H2020 Researchers’ Night** will be used to disseminate the results, but also F2F meetings with citizens, students, and schoolchildren in which through an informal interaction, our key messages will be conveyed. Meetings with the **representatives of professional organisations** such as IEEE and RSC will be used to share the outcomes of the **NANOFACTS**. Since NANOFACTS brings different research areas together, the meetings will be used to point out the multidisciplinary research, its benefits, and how they can contribute to the professional societies and help their evolution towards more need-driven and applied research. Such meetings will be typically collocated with the conferences since the high-impact conferences are organized by the most influential professional societies.

One of **NANOFACTS** priorities are **networking** activities **with other H2020 projects** with the similar topics and objectives. The experience and knowledge gained by similar projects will be a valuable tool for guidance of the project actions and will enhance the expertise of the project teams.

Meetings with other stakeholders includes SME and industry representatives who can benefit from the results of **NANOFACTS**. This will lead to better understanding of the potential for commercialization of our products and industry needs and transfer of knowledge from academia to industry.

6. Exploitation Strategy

NANOFACTS exploitation strategy is based on appropriate management of the generated Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), assessment of the expected impact and exploitation potential of the project results, and incorporation of individual exploitation plans for all partners. In Table 2, the major exploitable assets of the project, their type, and exploitation methods are summarized.

The project results are expected to be of sensitive nature and will have to be protected prior to dissemination so that the future **NANOFACTS** outcome will also retain a high commercial value apart from the foundation. The final decisions on IP protection are laid down in the Consortium Agreement and approved by all partners.

The partners will have full access to all data, which will be stored in databases local to where the related experiments have been conducted. These databases will be accessible (mirrored) to the consortium intranet but firewalled to prevent any external access. A Roadmap for Exploitation will be developed to plan for commercial and non-commercial use of **NANOFACTS** results (WP5).

Table 5: NANOFACTS Exploitation Strategy

Exploitable asset	Type	Exploitation action/IP to be created
New fundamental knowledge related to methodologies for targeted cancer therapy, construction of theranostic nanomaterials, biosensors for cancer diagnostics, cancer biomarkers, cancer tissue-specific environment, patient response to different types of treatments	Non-commercial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journal publication, proceedings, books • New research initiatives (e.g. H2020 calls) • New PhD courses • Further scientific breakthroughs in corresponding fields • Novel scientific solutions • Improvement of SME partners’ existing products or solutions

Novel nanomedicines New methodology for detection of cancer biomarkers directly in patients during therapy Novel cancer diagnostic platforms for detection of cancer biomarkers from patients' blood, saliva, breath etc.	Commercial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patent • Licensing agreement (royalty fees paid to researchers) • Contract research • Further development of prototypes to achieve TRL9 • Considering other business models for the commercialization
Advanced manufacturing methods for nanomedicines and diagnostic devices	Both	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journal publication, proceedings, books • Patent • Licensing agreement (royalty fees paid to researchers)
Soft skills (entrepreneurial, business planning, etc.)	Commercial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New research initiatives (e.g. H2020 calls) • Further development of prototypes to achieve TRL9 • Creating spin-offs

6.1.1 IPR Management

The management of IPR is strictly ruled by the Consortium and Partnership Agreements which includes the provisions related to the ownership of the results, access rights to the background and for implementation and exploitation, granting of access rights as well as questions of confidentiality, liability, and dispute settlement.

The agreements regulate the ownership of the results as follows:

Results are owned by the Party that generates them. In accordance with the first paragraph of Article 26.2 of the Grant Agreement, two or more Parties shall own Results jointly if:

(a) they have jointly generated them; and

(b) it is not possible to:

(i) establish the respective contribution of each Party; or

(ii) separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection.

The joint owners must agree in writing on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership ('joint ownership agreement'), to ensure compliance with their obligations under the GA.

Also, all partners have identified their background to which they will grant access rights for the implementation of the project or exploitation of any results. However, there shall be no obligation to grant, and no right to be granted, access rights to any background that is not identified by the partners.

Other provisions are confidential or out of scope of this report, and thus they will not be elaborated here.

7. Implementation

Dissemination and communication activities will span over the whole duration of the project (M01 – M36). Nevertheless, they will be intensified in periods of Project events. These events will be promoted before they begin, using the described dissemination tools. Also, their results will be promoted after they finish, to disseminate the conclusions and further steps.

1. **Science Slam** (5 min talk): Each PI will develop a 'Science Slam' on the specific discipline and research question addressed by **NANOFACTS**. These five-minute pitches will be recorded and posted on the website and be available for the university lectures.
2. **Scientific Symposium**: The academic partners will organize a Scientific Symposium as a satellite event at a key international cancer research conference to advertise **NANOFACTS** project results within the scientific community.

3. **Scientific Publications and Conference Presentations:** NANOFACTS is committed to open-access publishing. Communication of the results of NANOFACTS activities and further networking will be practiced through scientific publications in highly ranked journals, as well as through participation at relevant scientific conferences. Beginning in the second year of the project, NANOFACTS partners aim to present their results as invited keynote speakers at some of the most prestigious cancer research conferences such as the European Association for Cancer Research conferences.
4. **Workshops (WSs)** related to the scientific topic of the Project are to be organized on the fourth and fifth day of TS exclusively for BIOS researchers, while the third WS will be organized to cover training in project management and soft skills.
5. **Public relations:** To assess both the implementation and impact of the Dissemination and Outreach Plan (DOP), the consortium will routinely monitor and document all outreach activities.
6. **Industry relations Info days** will be organized during the Training School (TS) event to enhance the communication between the researchers and industry.
7. **Science Layman language Slam:** Each PhD student and ESR will communicate through NANOFACTS website and social media, in layman language, recent important scientific advances from the literature on the subject related to NANOFACTS scientific agenda. ESRs will also present their project in a layman language pitch on the specific discipline and research question addressed by NANOFACTS. These presentations will be recorded and posted on the website. The presentations in English and Serbian will be targeted to the general public, to help raise awareness for novel cancer therapies and highly innovative technologies with a wider audience.

7.1 Dissemination Tasks

The tasks, assigned to the WP6 (Dissemination and outreach activities) and their corresponding duration, are listed below:

- **Task 6.1: Dissemination strategy, plan and implementation** (Leader: BIOS; Participants: TCD, TUW; Duration: M01-M36). The target of this task is to develop a Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) and to assure the proper dissemination of project outcomes and provide to them an adequate spectrum of visibility. PEDR for promotion and dissemination will be defined, at an early stage, briefly outlining: the dissemination strategy itself, scope and specific objectives to be achieved, the identification of target group, the communication tools/instruments to be used for different audiences and time-plan. PEDR will ensure that project results will be adequately promoted to its targeted audiences, network of partners and interested parties.

- **Task 6.2: Dissemination tools and material** (Leader: BIOS; Participants: TCD, TUW; Duration: M01-M36). NANOFACTS will employ different strategy to promote Project and ensure that project results and knowledge will be communicated to its targeted audiences such as: the project website, the project brochure with basic information on the project, leaflets and posters for the WSs and fairs, pages and groups in various Social Media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn), presence in various TV and radio media, newspapers and magazine, etc. Information on the project will be updated frequently on website and social networks. All material will be developed in English, due to the fact that target groups defined are very diverse and widespread across the broader European region. However, a specific set of materials will be made in regional languages to ensure its uptake by the health sector within the region.

- **Task 6.3: Communication and stakeholder engagement strategy** (Leader: BIOS; Participants: TCD, TUW; Duration: M02-M36). The outreach activities will be agreed to promote a conducive environment for the engagement of general public, students and cancer patients at NANOFACTS events, to enhance the level of public understanding of the state-of-the-art scientific research. Journalists from the leading national and international media outlets will be invited to conduct interviews with the researchers at NANOFACTS events. NANOFACTS website will be created in M02 and all activities will be regularly updated. Popular news events will be frequently disseminated through different social media (Facebook, Twitter) while more professional social media such as LinkedIn and news outlets (Popular science, ScienceAlert, C&EN News) are to be used to communicate the NANOFACTS news to industrial stakeholders.

- **Task 6.4: Scientific dissemination** (Leader: TCD; Participants: BIOS, TUW; Duration: M12-M36). The activities and results of **NANOFACTS** will be disseminated through different scientific channels to scientists and general public, such as popular scientific websites (e.g. <https://phys.org/>). At least 20 journal and conference publications are expected during the course of the project.

7.2 Deliverables

The main deliverables that WP6 will yield are:

- **D6.1: PEDR – Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results:** The PEDR will be developed, at an early stage, outlining (among others) the dissemination strategy, the key communication messages and content to be used by **NANOFACTS** as well as to identify and employ the most suitable channels (Leader: BIOS, M02, Report, PU).
- **D6.2: NANOFACTS dissemination tools and material:** This report will summarise the communication materials produced during **NANOFACTS**, including online material, flyers, brochures, leaflets, posters, etc. (Leader: BIOS, M15, M35, R, PU).
- **D6.3: NANOFACTS Web-portal, and Social Media Groups:** Web and Social Media Groups will present a knowledge repository and communicator to promote project activities and results. (Leader: BIOS, M03, PU)
- **D6.4: Communication and public engagement:** This report will list all activities dedicated to the engagement of general public, students and cancer patients at **NANOFACTS** events (Leader BIOS; Participants: TCD, TUW, M18,36)
- **D6.5: Scientific Dissemination:** This deliverable will include all dissemination activities through publications in scientific journals and conferences (Leader TCD: Participants: TCD, TUW, BIOS, M18, M36, Report, PU)